

PLANNING AND ENGAGEMENT ARENAS FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY LANDSCAPES PEARLS

Marie Skłodowska - Curie Actions (MSCA)
Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE)
H2020-MSCA-RISE-2017 – 778039 - PEARLS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 778039.

Document Title	Case Studies
Version	1.0
Status	Version submitted to EC
Work Package	WP5
Deliverable Type	Report
Contractual Date of Delivery	2023-06-30
Actual Date of Delivery	2023-11-20
Responsible Unit	ICSUL
Contributors	USE; CLANER; Territoria; ICSUL; ENERCOUTIM; COOPERNICO; AUTH; GSH; BGU; UPO; E4G
Keyword List	Seminar; Energy Communities; Social Innovation
Dissemination level	Public

Changes record

Version	Date	Status	Author (Unit)	Description
0.1	2023/06/23	Draft	ICSUL	First Draft
0.2	2023/11/17	Draft	USE	Second Draft
0.3	2023/11/20	Draft	USE	Third Draft

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Abstract

The deliverable D 5.1. is a Seminar on Energy Communities for all partners involved in WP5. This seminar took place in hybrid form (at ICS and online) on the 20th June 2023. Researchers from ICSUL (PT), Coopernico (PT), Territoria (ES), Universidad Pablo de Olavide (ES), and Ethics for growth (IT) shared knowledge on energy communities, based on the secondments and the research work that has been conducted throughout the project.

The seminar was open to the public and was publicised in the usual channels of ICS and the Research Group SHIFT. 19 persons registered to participate online, 5 of them external to the project (4 from a Portuguese government agency of the energy sector). On the day of the seminar, 5 persons were present at ICS and 14 joined online. This report gives an account of the organisation of the seminar and the contents of the presentations.

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1. Introduction

WP5 Social Innovation and Public Engagement aims to reinforce the social dimension in renewable energy development. It aims to explore how resources from social research can be used to enhance the involvement of communities, to tap into local knowledge to create innovative solutions, to defuse potential causes for conflict around landscapes and cultural values.

WP5 is led by ICSUL (PT) and includes 11 other PEARLS partners: USE (ES), UPO (ES), CLANER (ES), Territoria (ES), ENERCOUTIM (PT), COOPERNICO (PT), AUTH (GR), GSH (GR) and Ben-Gurion University of the Negev (IL).

WP5 comprises three tasks:

- Task 1: Case studies of social innovation and entrepreneurship in the energy sector. This task consists of the identification of relevant cases of social innovation regarding renewable energy (novel more sustainable solutions to problems such as community opposition, landscape impacts, underdeveloped RE generation potential) through document analysis and interviews with stakeholders. A common template was designed for data collection in order to derive comparable information and best practices jointly with WP2 to WP4. Scientific paper on case studies of social innovation and entrepreneurship in the energy sector is under evaluation at the journal *Energy Research and Social Sciences*.
- Task 2. Landscape and cultural analysis. This task consists of developing studies on landscape and cultural factors in potential locations for renewable energy. Researchers will gather information on local cultural valuations of landscape and heritage in order to assess and anticipate potential conflicts and resistance to renewable energy facilities and help devise alternative locations or mitigation measures (through visual tools and other planning devices in cross cooperation with WP4).
- Task 3. Training in social analysis and participatory methods according to WP1 communication and dissemination strategy. This comprises the organisation of a methodological course on social analysis and participatory methods, aimed at researchers and technicians from business and civil society organisations (CSO), and a final integration seminar with all participants in the WP, which will take place at ICSUL

This deliverable concerns Task 3. It is an account of the seminar that was organised by ICSUL in June 2023. The report summarises the content of presentations, including the slides that were presented, and provides a brief reflexion on the results.

2. Organisation of the seminar

Task 3 of WP 5 Social Innovation consisted of training in social analysis and participatory methods, in line with WP1 communication and dissemination strategy. This comprises the organisation of a methodological course on social analysis and participatory methods aimed at researchers and technicians from business and civil society organisations (D5.1, completed in March 2023) and a final integration seminar with all participants in the WP, which took place at ICSUL in June 2023 (D 5.2).

As leader of WP5, ICSUL has been coordinating research work on energy communities in four of the participant countries in the project: Portugal, Spain, Italy and Greece. The work has been carried out during the secondments, combining the efforts of visiting researchers/technicians and host researchers/technicians. A report is under preparation, concerning the policy framework and present situation of energy communities and two case study summaries from each country. The presentations were mostly based on this report. The absence of Greece is due to a late start in fieldwork in this country.

Table 2.1. Biographies of presenters

Alekson Luz (Coopernico): He is a production technician at the cooperative Coopernico. He holds a Master degree in Energy and Environment from the Faculty of Sciences of the University of Lisbon.

Ricardo Iglesias (Univ. Pablo de Olavide): Associate Professor in the department of Geography, History and Philosophy. PhD since 2014, his main field of research is the analysis of inequalities and social challenges.

Mónica Truninger (ICSUL): Senior Research Fellow. She has a PhD in sociology (2006) from the University of Manchester. Her research interests are mainly in sustainable food consumption and provisioning systems, but she has also done research on renewable energies, the European Green Deal and public opinion on sustainability. She has been the national coordinator of several international projects funded on various topics such as sustainable food consumption, food freshness, food poverty and security, consumers' food safety practices. She has published widely in national and international journals. She currently leads the research group SHIFT – Environment, Territory and Society at ICS-ULisboa.

Giuseppe Macca (ethics4growth, Pi.Ro.Ca): Entrepreneur, passionate about sustainability and CSR expert, I have always dreamed about impacting the world. During my studies in political sciences at LUISS (Rome) I realize that one possible way of achieving it is by changing the way we do business. Travel addict, before getting back to Sicily, I had experiences in Buenos Aires, Sao Paulo, Boston Durham (UK). In 2020 I have launched the social innovation studio ethics4growth (<https://ethics4growth.com/>) and now I am also teaching Ethics and CSR in the faculty of international marketing of the University of Manizales (Colombia). I'm attending a PhD in economics at the University of Enna "Kore", investigating the performance of the Bcorps and the alternative development economic models.

Vera Ferreira (ICSUL): hD Candidate in Climate Change and Sustainable Development Policies at the Institute of Social Sciences of the University of Lisbon. She is a member of the Research Group on Environment, Territory and Society (SHIFT RG). Her thesis project is titled “The Portuguese energy transition in the 2050 horizon: an analysis through the energy democracy concept” and her current research interests include energy democracy and just energy transitions.

Ana Delicado (ICSUL): Senior Research Fellow. She has a PhD in sociology (2006) and she works mainly in social studies of science. She has been doing research on energy issues and climate change since 2010, in national and internationally funded projects. She is currently coordinating the ICSUL team in the projects PEARLS and PilotSTRATEGY CO2 Geological Pilots in Strategic Territories. She was a national delegate to COST Action TU 1401 "Renewable Energy and Landscape Quality (RELY)." She is particularly interested in public engagement with science.

Figure 2.2 Seminar programme

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PEARLS
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Seminar Energy Communities in Southern Europe
WP5 Social Innovation
20 June 2023

14.30 Welcome and introduction, Ana Delicado (ICS, PT)

15.00 Energy Communities in Portugal, Alekson Luz (Coopernico, PT) and Ricardo Iglesias (U. Pablo Olavide, ES)

15.30 Energy Communities in Spain, Monica Truninger (ICS, PT) and Michela Ghislanzoni (Territoria, ES)

16.00 Energy Communities in Italy, Giuseppe Macca (Ethics for Growth, IT) and Vera Ferreira (ICS, PT)

16.30 Final discussion

Venue: ICS, Room 2 and online

Registration (for online participation): <https://forms.office.com/e/v9w80sPMHF>

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Figure 2.1 shows the programme of the seminar. The date was set taking in account Ricardo Iglesias' secondment at Coopernico. There were no other researchers doing secondments in Lisbon at the time.

The seminar was advertised among the project partners and to the general public through the communication channels of ICS (website, social networks, weekly newsletter). A registration form was created for online participants, the face-to-face event was free admission. 19 persons registered to participate online, 5 of them external to the project (4 from a Portuguese government agency of the energy sector). Table 2.2 details their home institutions. The link for the Zoom sessions was sent to registered participants a few days before the seminar.

Table 2.2 Registered participants by organisation

Organisation	Number of participants
Coopérnico	3
Consortis	2
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	2
ICSUL	2
Universidad de Sevilla	2
ethics4growth	1
Universidad de Huelva	1
University of Trento	1
Other	5

3. Seminar

The seminar started at 2.30pm and ended at 5pm. Some speakers were in the room, others intervened through Zoom. 5 persons were present at ICS and 14 joined online. The order of presentations was slightly changed to accommodate requests from the presenters who had conflicting schedules: first Italy, second Spain and then Portugal. After the presentations from each country, the audience had the opportunity to ask questions to the speakers. The discussion was lively and relevant for improving the report that is being prepared. At the end of the seminar, the project coordinator, María-José Prados, proffered a final comment on the topic.

This section summarises the content of each presentation and includes the slides that were presented.

3.1 Introduction

The WP5 coordinator, Ana Delicado (ICSUL) began the seminar with a short introduction to the project PEARLS and to the topic of renewable energy communities. Definitions of social innovation, renewable energy communities and citizen energy communities, derived from European directives, were presented. The programme of the seminar was briefly introduced.

3.1.1 Presentation slides

Project

- Planning and Engagement Arenas for Renewable Energy Landscapes
- Funded by the EC through MSC RISE
- Led by Univ. Seville, 16 partners from 5 countries (Spain, Portugal, Italy, Greece, Israel), academic and non-academic
- WP5 Social Innovation and Public Engagement

Social innovation

"social innovation refers broadly to innovation in meeting social needs of, or delivering social benefits to, communities – the creation of new products, services, organizational structures or activities that are 'better' or 'more effective' than traditional public sector, philanthropic or market-reliant approaches in responding to social exclusion. (...) it means innovation in social relations. As such, we see the term as referring not just to particular actions, but also to the mobilization-participation processes and to the outcome of actions which lead to improvements in social relations, structures of governance, greater collective empowerment, and so on. (...) three [are] generic and interrelated features of social innovation: satisfaction of needs, reconfigured social relations and empowerment or political mobilization." (Moulaert et al. 2013)

Energy communities

- Energy cooperatives and energy communities as examples of social innovation in the field of renewable energy
- New initiatives that aim to bring energy production closer to the place of consumption (in houses, neighbourhoods, industrial and commercial buildings) and closer to the control of users

Benefits of energy communities

community energy and energy cooperatives [are] an effective and cost-efficient way to meet citizens' needs and expectations regarding energy sources, services and local participation. Community energy offers an inclusive option for all consumers to have a direct stake in producing, consuming or sharing energy between each other within a geographically confined community network that may operate in an isolated mode or be connected to the public distribution network. Community energy initiatives focus primarily on providing affordable energy of a specific kind, such as renewable energy, for their members or shareholders rather than prioritising profit-making like a traditional energy company. By directly engaging with consumers community energy initiatives are demonstrating their potential in facilitating the up-take of new technologies and consumption patterns, including smart distribution grids and demand response, in an integrated manner. Community energy can also advance energy efficiency at household level and help fight energy poverty through reduced consumption and lower supply tariffs. Community energy also enables certain groups of household consumers to participate in the energy market who otherwise might not have been able to do so. Where they have been successfully operated such initiatives have delivered economic, social and environmental value to the community that goes beyond the mere benefits derived from the provision of energy services.

(Directive COM(2016)864 of the European Parliament And Of The Council on common rules for the internal market in electricity)

Definition of RE communities

'renewable energy community' means a legal entity: (a) which, in accordance with the applicable national law, is based on **open and voluntary participation**, is autonomous, and is effectively controlled by shareholders or members that are located **in the proximity of the renewable energy** projects that are owned and developed by that legal entity; (b) the shareholders or members of which are **natural persons, SMEs or local authorities**, including municipalities; (c) the primary purpose of which is to provide **environmental, economic or social community** benefits for its shareholders or members or for the local areas where it operates, rather than financial profits.

Directive (EU) 2018/2001

Definition of citizen energy communities

'citizen energy community' means a legal entity that: (a) is based on voluntary and open participation and is effectively controlled by members or shareholders that are **natural persons, local authorities, including municipalities, or small enterprises**; (b) has for its primary purpose to provide **environmental, economic or social community benefits** to its members or shareholders or to the local areas where it operates rather than to generate financial profits; and (c) may engage in **generation, including from renewable sources, distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation, energy storage, energy efficiency services or charging services for electric vehicles or provide other energy services** to its members or shareholders;

Directive (EU) 2019/944

Seminar

- Energy Communities in Portugal: Alekson Luz (Coopernico, PT) and Ricardo Iglesias (U. Pablo Olavide, ES)
- Energy Communities in Spain: Monica Truninger (ICS, PT) and Michela Ghislanzoni (Territoria, ES)
- Energy Communities in Italy: Giuseppe Macca (Ethics for Growth, IT) and Vera Ferreira (ICS, PT)

3.2 Energy communities in Portugal

Two presentations gave a brief outline of state of the art in terms of energy communities in Portugal. The first, by Alekson Luz (Coopernico), after a short overview of the history and activities of the cooperative, addressed the case of a renewable energy community in the North of Portugal, Vila Boa do Bispo. He explained the process of setting up the energy community, the involvement of different partners, and the legal framework.

The second presentation, by Ricardo Iglesias (Univ. Pablo de Olavide), focused on the case of São Luís, one of the first energy communities that emerged in Portugal, even before the

regulation of these organisations. He explained what he found in fieldwork done in 2019 and 2023, the challenges faced by the project and its future prospects.

3.2.1 Presentation slides: first presentation

1. ABOUT US

- Coopérnico was created with the single goal – to promote renewable energy by the empowerment of citizens. So what we want to achieve is:
- A fair and responsible **energy model based on renewables;**
- To contribute to a social, environmental and energetic **sustainable future;**
- To **involve citizens and companies** in the creation of a new energy paradigm - renewable and decentralized - for the benefit of society and the environment.

1. HOW DO WE START?

- 2012: A group of 16 citizen friends wanted to invest their savings responsibly - renewable energy
- Identified model: establishment of a renewable energy cooperative (late 2013)
- Set of interesting projects from a social, environmental and economic point of view

1. OUR COMMITMENTS

100% green energy

All electricity is produced exclusively from renewable energy sources

Social Value creation

All our projects create social value, either by close collaboration or the sharing of revenues with organizations operating in the social economy

Developing local economy

When we develop a new project we prioritize local partners. This creates local jobs and promotes the transition to a sustainable economy

Integrity and transparency

They are the basis for long and trusting relationships. Updated information on our projects is shared with all the members that have supported them

1. ABOUT WHAT WE DO

Coopérnico focuses its efforts in three main areas of activity:

- **Production** of renewable energy (so far only PV);
- **Supplier:** the only cooperative supplying electricity in Portugal
- **Energy Efficiency:**
 - Self-consumption for members (PV);
 - Tackle Energy Poverty;
 - Energy Communities.

1. PRODUCTION

34 DECENTRALIZED PV PROJECTS
2,2 MWp INSTALLED
2,1 M€ INVESTED

1. SUPPLY

Empowerment of Citizens

The first renewable energy cooperative as energy supplier in Portugal

The Dream: Production > Energy consumption of our members

1. COOPERNICO TODAY

>3880

2,1 M€

2,2 MWp

>2733

2. RENEWABLE ENERGY COMMUNITIES SUPPORTED BY COOPÉRNICO

- Alta de Lisboa;
- Vila Boa do Bispo;
- COMSOLVE;
- Telheiras;
- Oeiras

[Coopérnico - Nasceu a primeira Comunidade de Energia Renovável numa freguesia \[coopernico.org\]](#)

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2.REC - VILA BOA DO BISPO Framing

- Vila Boa do Bispo REC is located in the Santa Maria Urbanization, within the Vila Boa do Bispo Parish. It is a parish with approximately 3049 inhabitants and an area of 11,71 km².
- The parish's rural surroundings and location underscore values of proximity and engagement.
- The establishment of a renewable energy community represents an innovative initiative for the locality, serving as a response to the energy and environmental challenges of the present time.

[Coopérnico - Nasceu a primeira Comunidade de Energia Renovável numa freguesia \[coopernico.org\]](#)

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2. REC - VILA BOA DO BISPO Framing

- The first contacts on the topic were made between the Vila Boa do Bispo Parish Council and Coopérnico in 2020.
- The REC will be initially constituted by a public entity, the Vila Boa do Bispo Parish Council (1 consumption point), and two non-profit organizations, the Cultural and Sports Association of Casa do Povo de Vila Boa do Bispo (2 consumption points), and the Volunteer Firefighters Humanitarian Association of Vila Boa do Bispo (1 consumption point).

[Coopérnico - Nasceu a primeira Comunidade de Energia Renovável numa freguesia \(coopernico.org\)](https://coopernico.org)

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2. REC - VILA BOA DO BISPO PRODUCTION vs CONSUMPTION

- A 17kWp photovoltaic solar system will be installed on the roof of the Volunteer Firefighters of Vila Boa do Bispo, with an estimated production of 23,34 MWh per year.
- The energy production will be sharing between 4 consumption points belonging to the 3 entities of the REC, according to a sharing coefficient proportional to consumption. This will enable a global self-consumption of 97% and an energy saving of 25%.

[Coopérnico - Nasceu a primeira Comunidade de Energia Renovável numa freguesia \(coopernico.org\)](https://coopernico.org)

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2. REC - VILA BOA DO BISPO LEGAL FORM

- The chosen legal form for the establishment of the REC was a Public Interest Cooperative.
- The creation of a Public Interest Cooperative did not pass the Court of Auditors.
- To overcome this bureaucratic obstacle, the possibility of creating an Association is being studied.
- The objective is to find a legal format that allows any entity whether individual or collective to participate in the REC.

2. REC - VILA BOA DO BISPO COOPÉRNICO'S ROLE

- Technical support from Coopernico, through preliminary studies to assess the project and simulate impacts;
- Legal support in assisting with the creation of internal regulations;
- Legal support in the establishment and constitution of the REC, and selection of the legal format.

THE FUTURE

- The energy transition is inevitable, and the challenges are enormous. The path in this transition must involve citizens with their direct participation.
- The variety of entities participating in the energy sector makes the sector more dynamic and robust.
- Energy cooperatives with direct citizen participation demonstrate that citizens have an interest in building alternative solutions for energy production and consumption.

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THANK YOU!!!

If you need more info:

- +351 967 189 750
- adluz@coopernico.org
- www.coopernico.org

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3.2.2 Presentation slides: second presentation

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Energy Communities in Portugal:

The Case of Sao Luis: The “Terra incognita” between Alentejo and Algarve

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BACKGROUND AND ORIGIN

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BACKGROUND AND ORIGIN:

. In 2012, this energy project began as a result of a citizens' initiative submitted to Odemira's participatory budget call and was awarded 125,000 euros.

Project submitted by a small, isolated and informal group

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. In 2017, a study of the locality's energy needs and a collective neighbourhood purchase of solar panels was carried out

Cooperativa Minga

Coopernico

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. In 2012, this energy project began as a result of a citizens' initiative submitted to Odemira's participatory budget call and was awarded 125,000 euros

. In 2017, a study of the locality's energy needs and a collective neighbourhood purchase of solar panels was carried out

. Installation of solar panels on the roofs of the Sociedade Musical Recreativa de São Luis, the Junta Parroquial, the Casa do Pueblo and around the local government.

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STATUS OF THE PROJECT IN MY FIRST SECONDMENTS DURING 2019

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STATUS OF THE PROJECT DURING 2019:

. The participatory process was organised through a social collective composed of residents and non-residents of Sao Luis, called the Sao Luis Transition Movement.

Main actors: members of the University of Lisbon, Sergio Maraschin, president of the freguesia of Sao Luis.

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STATUS OF THE PROJECT DURING 2019 :

- . The participatory process was organised through a social collective composed of residents and non-residents of Sao Luis, called the Sao Luis Transition Movement.
- . The neighbourhood and collective purchase of the solar panels together with the support of the local government of Sao Luis and the Sociedade Musical Recreativa San Luizense, showed the democratic, community and horizontal character of this energy project.
- . The deliberative process lasted more than four months. The self-organised nature of the initiative, with a horizontal management system based on voluntary work, enriched the social process and, at the same time, delayed decision-making.

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STATUS OF THE PROJECT DURING 2019 :

Key supports over time:

- Coopernico cooperative (e.g. technical support and PhD thesis of Luis Cachinho).
- European project H 2020, PROSEU, focused on promoting the integration of the renewable energy prosumer phenomenon within the European Energy Union.

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STATUS OF THE PROJECT DURING 2019 :

Social effects and repercussions:

This energy project has also had cultural and educational implications with the development of:

- Artistic and musical activities involving in Sao Louis (<https://montrassauluis.wixsite.com/2019>)
- Training workshops on the installation and development of renewable energies, as well as participatory sessions for the design of community energy.

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PERCEPTIONS AND DOUBTS AFTER THE JUNE 2019 SECONDMENT:

- Will the horizontal and community character be a potential or a burden for the project?
- Will the public support of the fregesia and the council of Odemira be maintained over time?
- Is the management of the process mainly exogenous and expert knowledge or is there a real community participation?

Could be the Sao Louis project a model for a possible energy democracy in Portugal?

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CURRENT PROJECT STATUS:

IMPASSE FROM COVID-19

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CURRENT PROJECT STATUS:

Great expectations:

Six thousand square metres ceded by
Odemira council for the installation of solar
panels

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CURRENT PROJECT STATUS:

Today's harsh reality:

Need to temporarily transfer the space promised for the location of the local school due to the poor state of the current building.

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CURRENT PROJECT STATUS:

Delay until at least 2024 in the construction of the new school.

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RENEWABLE ENERGY LANDSCAPES
H2020-MSCA-RISE-2017 – 778039-PEARLS

Seminar Energy Communities in Southern Europe

WP5 Social Innovation

20 June 2023

CURRENT PROJECT STATUS:

Result:

COVID, administrative difficulties and bad luck explain why the project has not progressed since 2019.

Consequences and challenges:

- Possible exhaustion of the external leaders who played a leading role in the implementation of the project?
- Need to involve the local community more in decision-making?
- Importance of trying to consolidate the project by acquiring the legal status of community energy?

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Thanks for your attention.

Contact riglpa@upo.es

3.3 Energy Communities in Spain

In the absence of Michela Ghislanzoni (Territoria), who had previous commitments, Monica Truninger (ICSUL) presented the results of the work they had been conducting since 2019 on Spanish energy communities. She started by mentioning the delays in policy that hindered the development of the communities, then presented the characteristics of existing or in planning communities. Afterwards, two cases studies of renewable energy communities were discussed, one in a rural setting, another in an urban one.

3.3.1 Presentations slides

Energy Communities in Spain

Monica Truninger (ICS, PT) and Michela Ghislanzoni (Territoria, ES)

Seminar Energy Communities in Southern Europe WP5 Social Innovation
ICS-ULisboa, 20 June 2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska Curie grant agreement No 778039.

U LISBOA | UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA

ICS INSTITUTO DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS

fct Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia

Legal framework: a brief overview

- In 2018, the newly elected socialist government repealed the "sun tax" (Real Decreto 15/2018), which was a severe obstacle to solar photovoltaic projects.
- In 2019, the Real Decreto 244/2019 sets the administrative, technical, and economic conditions of self-consumption of electricity, including collective presumption.
- In 2020, the Real Decreto-ley 23/2020 contains several measures regarding energy due to the pandemic situation and is the first to include the definition of renewable energy communities (similar to the one in the EU Directive).
- In 2021, the Real Decreto 477/2021 defines the conditions for several incentive programs linked to prosumption and storage, with renewable energy sources, as well as the implementation of renewable thermal systems in the residential sector.
- In April 2023 the government presented for public discussion a draft of a new law concerning RE communities and citizen energy communities that would finally regulate their operation.

IDAE funded energy communities (73)

> 180 REC in Spain (Aliante Alianza Energía y Territorio)

REC: main features

- Mainly photovoltaic (often solar panels installed on the rooftops of public buildings, such as schools and sports facilities),
- A few rely on hydraulic and biomass energy. Most REC, but some are also Citizen Energy Communities.
- Large majority supported by Energy cooperatives (Goener, SomEnergia, ...)
- Most rely on wide partnerships that involve regional and municipal authorities, SMEs, civil society organisations and residents. Many REC are based on participatory processes.
- Some large companies already provide support to REC, such as Vagalume Energía.

Case Study 1: Alumbra, Arroyomolinos de Leon

Case Study 1: Alumbra, Arroyomolinos de Leon

First session of the Alumbra Energy Community, January 2020, planting of a symbolic tree.

Case study 2: Torreblanca, Seville

Case study 2: Torreblanca, Seville

Photo: School in Torreblanca.

3.4 Energy Communities in Italy

The situation of energy communities in Italy was the topic of two presentations. The first, by Giuseppe Macca (ethics4growth), who opted for not showing slides, addressed the legal framework of energy communities in Italy and then proceeded to present the case of FERLA, an energy community in Sicily, initiated by the municipality. The second presentation, by Vera Ferreira (ICSUL), focused on the case of the energy community “La Buona Fonte”, in Riccomassimo, a village in the mountains of Northern Italy, which was awarded the distinction of ‘most innovative REC in Italy’ by the Italian Forum of Energy Communities.

3.4.1 Presentation slides: second presentation

Energy Communities in Italy

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PEARLS
EMPOWERING LOCAL SOCIETIES

INSTITUTO DE CIÊNCIAS SOCIAIS

Seminar Energy Communities in Southern Europe

Institute of Social Sciences, University of Lisbon

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Vera Ferreira
PhD Candidate in Climate Change and
Sustainable Development Policies

CER “La Buona Fonte” Riccomassimo – a preliminary analysis

- First renewable energy cooperative (REC) in the region of Trentino-Alto Adige.
- Small mountain village of 51 inhabitants in the Municipality of Storo, Province of Trento.
- Officially inaugurated on July 16, 2021.
- Project implemented by :
 - CEDIS (electricity cooperative): initial investment; legal and technical assistance.
 - La Buona Fonte (association for social promotion): legally represents the REC; engine of community and local development.
- Most residents joined the association and the REC: 26 end users are connected.

Why Riccomassimo?

- 2020: call for partners for a study on energy communities launched by Ricerca sul Sistema Elettrico.
- Successful application by CEDIS.
- Riccomassimo was identified as a suitable pilot site:
 - Availability of a public building for the installment of a photovoltaic system;
 - Existence of a unified, vibrant, and supportive community.

Timeline

“Most innovative REC in Italy” (Italian Forum of Energy Communities, 2022)

- Avoid depopulation.
- Bolster the social, cultural, environmental and energy development of the territory.
- Implement projects aimed at enhancing the historical and cultural heritage of the region.
- Offer services to the community.
- Proceeds will be reinvested in the territory and the community.
- Projects:
 - Renovation of a small church in the village;
 - Maintenance of mountain trails;
 - Urban beautification.
- Winner of the Call prize: donation of €2400 to develop the REC.

Thank you for your attention!

vera.ferreira@ics.ulisboa.pt

4. Results

The seminar achieved most of the expected results. It gave project members the opportunity to show the results of their research, discussed them with partners, some of whom not directly involved in WP5, exchange experiences and showcase the benefits of international and inter-sectorial secondments.

Although we did not perform an evaluation of the seminar, the questions posed during and at the end of the seminar showed that participants were motivated and interested. The seminar was well attended and contributed to improve the report that is being prepared on the topic, as well as future conference presentations and academic publications on the topic of renewable energy communities.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that this a very popular topic at the moment and a wider audience would be expected. Not all registered participants actually attended and it was unfortunate that the Greek cases could not be yet discussed.

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